

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Том 2, Выпуск 2, 29 Февраль

EFFECT OF SPORTS PARTICIPATION BY THE PARENT ON PHYSICAL FITNESS OF THEIR CHILD

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Abstract: The objective of the present study was to analyze the Influence of selected socio-economic condition factor, “sports participation by the parent” on Physical Fitness of college Female students. With the assistance and help of the experts in the field of Physical Fitness, Physical Education, Sports and previous researches on these areas, a comprehensive and suitable Physical Fitness and Socio-economic factor package was evolved. 500 Female college students were randomly selected from twenty one academic colleges of Saurashtra University. For this research, AAHPERED Youth Fitness Test for Physical Fitness and Questionnaire for Socio-economic condition data of the same students was organized for the purpose of finding out the effect of “sports participation by the parent” on Physical Fitness. The obtained Physical Fitness score and Socio-economic condition factor, “sports participation by the parent” score were analyzed by using analysis of covariance for significant influence of “sports participation by the parent” on Physical Fitness. The researcher has studied all samples in two groups. The groups were as below; A. Rural and Urban area all students. B. Tribal and non-tribal area all students. Analysis the data by use of SPSS programme and find out the mean score of sports achievement by the members of the family, meanscore of Physical Fitness of the sample and "F" values in all four groups and compare the result. The calculated 'F' value of rural area all students is 1.634, Non-tribal area all students is 1.641 and were significant at both 0.01 and 0.05 levels whereas tribal area all students is 1.531, were significant at 0.05 levels. Urban area all students is 0.758 not significant at both levels.

Keywords: Physical Fitness, ST & Non-ST, Sports Participation

1. INTRODUCTION: Physical Fitness is one's richest possession; it can't be purchased but can be earned through a daily routine of physical exercise. Earlier physical fitness means the capacity of an individual to perform given physical task involving muscular efforts. But this narrow concept of Physical Fitness has undergone

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a change, now a new concept of "Physical Fitness" is evolved. According to AАНPERD, "Physical Fitness means that state which characterizes the degree to which the person is able to function". Ability to function depends upon the physical, mental, social and spiritual components of fitness, all of which are related to each other and also mutually inter-dependent. Adequate level of Physical Fitness should be developed early in life and then continuously maintained through regular participation in a well-designed activity programmed to promote the total well being of an individual. Children should be fit for participation in the play activities of childhood, through which they develop organic vigor, strength and other fitness qualities. Fitness is the basic need for participation in games & sports. So, it is universally accepted that success in various activities of games and sports mainly depends upon the physical fitness of its participants. The basic level of fitness has a vital role in improving any sport performance but there seems to be a lack of specific knowledge regarding effect of sports achievements of the family members on the Physical Fitness of their child. It has been a matter of great concern for the sports teacher and coaches to assess the effect of sports achievements of the family members on Physical Fitness of their wards. In order to accomplish this, I studied "Effect of sports participation by the parent on Physical Fitness of their child" Significance of the study: Even though increasing recognition to Physical Fitness for health and efficiency is forth coming all over the world, still a lot of promotional and educative efforts are called for to bring about desirable attitudes especially in the youth, college going students towards physical activities and sports to develop Physical Fitness. If we view in the field of physical education and sports, physical fitness plays a major role. The sportsman who doesn't have optimum level of physical fitness cannot face the competition successfully. Some parameters such as family support, financial, moral, education and sports background of the family could also assist in the overall fitness as well as performance of their child. Inter-personal relationship with residential status, mode of stay and involvement of family members may lead to lack of support to participate in sports practice. The desired goals can be achieved better in sports performance, if the members of the family are also involved in sports and games participation. In absence of it, sportsperson as well as the society will suffer a greater lose. Physical Fitness is the basic need for participation in games & sports. The basic level of fitness has a vital role in improving any sport performance but there seems to be a lack of specific knowledge regarding "Effect of sports

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participation by the parent on Physical Fitness of their child". So, the study intends to identify the effect of sports achievement by the members of the family on physical fitness of their child in tribal and non-tribal area.

Purpose of the study: The purpose of present study was to compare the "Effect of sports participation by the parent on Physical Fitness of their child".

2. METHODOLOGY: Subject: Subjects selected for this study were four hundred eighty Female students from twenty one academic colleges of Saurashtra University at randomly. The average age of the subjects were twenty years, ranging from 19-23 years.

Variables: The research scholar reviewed the available scientific literature pertain to the socio-economic condition and Physical Fitness from the books, journals, periodicals, magazines and research papers and listed down the important socio-economic condition factors and Physical Fitness Test. The experts in the field of Physical Education and Sports were consulted and detailed discussions were held related to the Physical Fitness and socio-economic condition variable. On the bases of review of related literature, expert's opinions and research scholar's own understanding of Physical Fitness and socio-economic condition, the following variables were selected for the purpose of this study.

Independent variable: AAHPERD Youth Fitness Test total score.

Dependent variables: Sports participation by parent.

Statistical Analysis: The data obtained by various criterion measures for Physical Fitness and socio-economic condition variable " sports participation by the parent" score were subjected to the statistical methods in order to compare with four groups which are given as below; A. Rural and Urban area all students. B. Tribal and non-tribal area all students. As per statistic study, ANOVA test were done. Where the value of „F“ was found and compared with tabulated „F“ value. The level of significance was kept at 0.01 and 0.05

3. FINDINGS: TABLE Total samples, mean score of sports achievements by the members of the family, mean score of Physical Fitness of the sample, "F" value, significant level at 0.05 and significant level at 0.01 in all four groups. Group-1 Group-2 Rural area all Urban area all Tribal area all Non-tribal area all Total number of samples N 446 34 206 274 Mean score of Sports achievement 1.70 3.08 1.43 2.08 Mean score of Phy. Fit. 32.25 25.77 30.95 32.42 Calculated "F" Value **1.634 0.758 *1.531 **1.641 Tabulated Sig. level at 0.05 1.32 3.81 1.37 1.35 Tabulated Sig. level at 0.01 1.47 7.23 1.56 1.53

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4. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS: On the basis of the findings shown in table following discussion may be drawn as below: GROUP-1 As shown in Table, calculated 'F' value of rural area all students is 1.634, this is significant at both 0.01 and 0.05 level and urban area all students is 0.758, this is not significant at both 0.01 and 0.05 levels. In comparison to rural area all students and urban area all students, sports participation by the parent have significant affect Physical Fitness of rural area all students whereas there is not significantly affect Physical Fitness of urban area all students. GROUP-2 As shown in Table, calculated 'F' value of tribal area all students is 1.531, this is significant at 0.05 level and Non-tribal area all students is 1.641, this is significant at both 0.01 and 0.05 levels. In comparison to tribal and non-tribal area all students, sports participation by the parent have significant affect Physical Fitness of tribal area all students at 0.05 level, whereas there is significant affect Physical Fitness of Non-tribal area all students at both 0.01 and 0.05 levels.

5. CONCLUSIONS:

On the basis of the findings shown in table, sports participation by the parent significantly affect Physical Fitness of rural area all, tribal area all, non-tribal area all, college students, whereas did not significantly affect urban area all college students.

REFERENCE:

- [1] Bucher Charles A. and Read Evelyn M., "Physical Education and Health in Elementary School", (New York: The Macmillan Co., 1964).
- [2] Clark Harrison H. and Clarke David H., "Application of measurement to Physical Education". (Englewood Cliffs, N. J. Prentice Hall Inc., 1987).
- [3] Dominick A. Taddonio, "A Comparison of Physical Fitness of Public School Students from Economically Deprived Areas with Nation Norms, Dissertation Abstracts International 43:6 (December 1982).
- [4] Jacobs and Starns, Satygrah Sidhantalankar - Human Sociology - Lakhanpal, (1978).
- [5] John Lee Stock Hill "A study of junior high schoolboys Physical Fitness Scores related to the Nieman David C. & P. H. Facsm, "Fitness and Sports Medicine: A Health Related Sarkar L.N. and Nityanand Karmakar, "A comparative study of selected physical, physiological, Anthropometrics and Psychological Variables between caesarean and naturally born.